

CLIMATE CHANGE - A NEW LOOK

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The phrase “climate change” is probably the most frequently heard phrase in these days of scientific control of the technical media. Many people do not know its full meaning. And most who think more about this phrase have not been allowed to voice their own independent conclusions as to its veracity, due to the view of the scientists taking precedence. Scientists do not know all the reasons or all the answers.

Hence it is necessary to bring in a balance where we live in an age in which the scientists are the gods of the modern world. In times past various other authorities were recognised as “gods” or authority for human guidance. Now it seems that the scientists have taken over this rôle as unelected leaders of many government decisions.

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INTRODUCTION

We live in an age of huge national government cost of scientific research; nearly £40 billion in 2022 in the UK, which is more than £1,000 per income tax payer. Yet if the reality behind my paper “Human Mental Blindness” (HMB) is understood, we must be cautious about the conclusions which scientists throw out from their attempts to understand the world in which we live. There is not one person on this planet who has not been a victim of HMB many times in their life. Human mental blindness is both prevalent and contagious. It is also almost unknown and unrecognised; and will always result in false conclusions being reached, with the added dimension that many who reach such conclusions, believe in them and are prepared to put them into the public arena. When such scientists are paid for their work by governments (i.e. the tax payers), then the policies of the nation are likely to be formed from these incorrect conclusions. Unelected people can become the main influence or control of government policies. Hence it is important to examine the veracity and compass of current climate science.

[Human Mental Blindness (HMB) at -- <https://www.academia.edu/45180280/>]

REFLECTION

In early 1977 a genius of an Englishman had a vision in which he foresaw the future of many things. His name was Douglas Adams. So clear, scary and detailed was his vision that he found difficulty in knowing how to present it to the public. Eventually he produced his vision in a BBC UK radio program in 1978. It was called, “The Hitchhikers Guide to the Galaxy” (HGTTG). Within this strange program were contained predictions of search engines (came in 1982) and the World Wide Web (came in 1989), and the destruction of the planet Earth. The idea of the book called “The Hitchhikers Guide to the Galaxy” was what the internet eventually became. He described a comprehensive electronic book which had access to all knowledge and information, simply by taping in an access code. This is what we do; which was not predicted by anyone else in his time.

But the main character in the beginning of the story is a man called Arthur Dent. It starts with a scene which predicted the current situation with "climate change", but it was not depicted as climate but instead by the fact that Arthur Dent's house was about to be demolished. Arthur was panicking about an event which he could not prevent happening. Within the first episode the whole scene was set. What Arthur did not know was that the whole planet earth was about to be destroyed, and he would soon be going across the galaxy to other worlds, where he would find a new life. So his little panic was put into perspective. Likewise I will try to put the climate change panic into perspective.

Mankind across the planet is currently panicking about the rise in air temperature and the possible threat to organic life which may result. What mankind cannot see, and does not know, is that the Earth as a home for organic life will eventually end and the small panic about temperature will pale into insignificance; just as with Arthur's house panic compared to the destruction of the planet he was living on. Also mankind will go to other planets and start a new life wherever he wills. But this travel will not be in space ships.

Above I have attempted to show the plan of this paper and what to expect later on.

THE CAUSE OF CLIMATE

The sun is the main cause of climate on the planet Earth. Yet what is the sun?

Scientists View :- "Our Sun is a 4.5 billion-year-old star - a hot glowing ball of hydrogen and helium at the centre of our solar system. The Sun is about 93 million miles (150 million kilometres) from Earth, and without its energy, life as we know it could not exist here on our home planet. " -- by NASA.

The distance from the earth can be verified i.e. actually calculated. In the 19th century scientists put the age of the sun at 20 million years. Now it is 4.5 billion (i.e. 2,250 times older in 120 years or so). But any age of the sun cannot possibly be verified with the same degree of certainty as its distance from the Earth. The NASA age is only an "estimate", but the description does not use this word - i.e. it is stated as fact, not an estimate. What will the estimate be next century? What is a year? Does it entail a fixed idea of change?

If any thinking person really hears the above phrase "*hydrogen and helium*" they may ask, "*Which scientists went to the sun and brought back a container with these gases in it?*" Surely we know the scientists cannot prove that these two gases are the entire content of the sun. The NASA description also states that the core temperature is 15 million°C. How can any human being make such a statement? This number has no meaning which the ordinary person can make sense of (as with 4.5 billion years). Also it is a measure that cannot be made by any scientific instrument. And it is in a place where no scientist or machine can ever visit. Hence it cannot be verified. Are we really to believe the whole content of the NASA description? Are they suffering from HMB? However, the temperature which may be of more interest for this paper is 5,500°C, the temperature of the sun's outer surface, as stated by the scientists. I may use this presumed data later on.

Another View :- Ancient civilisations of this planet viewed the sun very differently to the above view of modern science. This ancient view did not change every century. They could not think of the sun as a mere physical object in the sky. Using simple common sense they could see that :- "*life as we know it could not exist here on our home planet.*" They did not need to be scientists to come that conclusion. Hence, for thousands of years, the sun was for them as a deity or a god in the sky, to whom they could direct their worship. And according to men greater than the average person, the ancient peoples were given good reasons to view the sun as a living being; a view established for many centuries.

Part of a statement made by a divine incarnation of the Creator of the universe, reads:-

“The light which residing in the sun illumines the whole world, know that light to be Mine. ” (mine = the Creator’s)

Spoken by the Lord Shri Krishna, from Bhagavad Gita Chapter 15 verse 12; originated many thousands of years ago.

Another one more recent, by another incarnation of the Creator :-

“The sun rises that it may warm you during your labour; it sets that it may give you the hours of rest I have myself fixed. ” (myself fixed = I am in control of sun and earth.)

Said by Jesus Christ - taken from “The Unknown life of Christ” by Nicolas Notovich - from records of Jesus’ life held in a Tibetan monastery.

[See - The Unknown life of Christ at <https://www.academia.edu/76935740/> page 80]

The above quoted statements are really by the One who created the sun as part of the universe. Who are we to countermand such statements? We have no authority to do so.

A very authoritative scripture called the Yoga Vasishtha clarifies without doubt, that the sun is a living being, which has both intelligence and consciousness :-

9:22 - The bodiless spirit takes upon it the great body of the sun and illuminates all the worlds with their minute particles while it (the bodiless spirit) remains quiet in itself (i.e. unaffected by the extreme heat of its own body).

27:12 - I am the intellect which resides in the sun and in the sky (space). I am the consciousness which dwells in the bodies of all beings. (I = Creator)

8:10 - It is the spiritual light of the soul which exists from before the light of vision, and which is derived from the light of the sun. (i.e. sun = Creator)

30:50 - It is by the power of this great Consciousness that the sun and other luminous bodies shine in the sky. (meaning the sun is consciousness).

From “The Unknown Life of Jesus Christ. ” VIII:15-16 :-

“The sun cannot act of its own accord, but only by the Will of the Creator, who is both intangible and incomprehensible to you. It is He who has given the sun both its existence and power. It is He alone whose Will has given the light and heat from the sun to warm the labour and the crops of man. ” Words of Jesus.

Download “Unknown Life of Jesus Christ” at <https://www.academia.edu/76935740/>

The scientist’s view is that the sun is merely a physical object; yet they do say that all life depends on it. The ancient view is that it carries out the Will of the Creator; hence it must be alive; not merely a physical object. Lumps of rock cannot carry out His Will.

If in place of the sun there was instead an equivalent mass of cold rock, with all the planets revolving around in darkness, there would be no life on the planet Earth. If the presence or not of the hot shining sun is the difference between life or no life, then the sun must be a living being. We cannot exchange the sun for the dark cold situation and think that it is as dead as the cold lump of rock. The sun is clearly living and conscious.

If it is responsible for, or the cause of, “*life as we know it*” how can it be dead? The sun must be a living being. It is true that no organic “*life as we know it*” could continue to live on (or near) the sun, but that does not mean we should limit the word “*life*” to those things which we see as animations on the earths surface. Life is basically consciousness, which cannot be burned, since it is not a material thing. For the sun to carry out any function which creates conscious beings, itself must be conscious. Hence it must also have intelligence. No dead physical matter, acting alone on the Earth’s surface, has ever

produced conscious intelligent creatures. Only that which is alive and is conscious can itself create another being which is alive and conscious.

It is a very different view to envisage the sun as consciousness which creates life; instead of being a ball of lifeless "hydrogen and helium". We need to dump this scientific view if we really wish to understand what the sun is and its true function here. The risk that scientists are suffering from HMB is too great for us to rely on their statements. Scientist's view consciousness as an object somewhere within the brain, they do not realise they are using it to look for itself. Consciousness is the subject (the one looking) not an object. Hence HMB arises. In times past, the view of greater people who have had a real vision of the workings of the universe, was considered far more reliable than such temporary theories of scientists.

Hence I conclude the sun is a living, intelligent and conscious being which is well aware of what is happening to the climate on the planet Earth. And, with its intelligence, has the power to regulate or control it as part of the overall plan.

THE PLANET EARTH - IS IT EXPANDING OR SHRINKING?

Scientists View :- "At its beginning, Earth was unrecognizable from its modern form. At first, it was extremely hot, to the point that the planet likely consisted almost entirely of molten magma. Over the course of a few hundred million years, the planet began to cool and oceans of liquid water formed. Heavy elements began sinking past the oceans and magma toward the centre of the planet." National Geographic.

What scientists don't seem to realise is, that such statements as above are self contradictory. According to them the Earth apparently begun as a large molten mass. Molten or liquid materials take on a spherical shape due to surface tension, hence the Earth would have been spherical. This magma is similar to any molten metal. When metals cool they typically shrink by about 2% or more of their volume. This 2% is related to the molten temperature reducing from about 1,200°C to 25°C. But scientists are saying that the Earth formed from magma at 5,500°C, then later cooled to have oceans on its surface. With most of the Earth's mantle reported as being 1,500°C to 2,500°C or more, this would produce a volume reduction of around 8% to 10% at least.

We all know the shape of an inflated balloon. Also we have all seen one which has reduced in volume losing its spherical shape.

The Earth is currently showing a very spherical shape. Which would indicate that it is undergoing a process of being inflated. If it had been molten and much hotter hundreds of millions of years ago, the outer surface may have formed a harder skin, but the continual reduction in its temperature over all that time would cause the surface to lose its spherical appearance, due to shrinkage of its mass.

The current theories of the Earth being originally molten magma and cooling to its current condition, cannot satisfy common sense with regard to the current very spherical shape of the land mass we have seen from pictures taken in outer space. Hence I conclude that there is strong evidence for the Earth going through a process of expansion, not shrinking.

This expansion of the Earth, including its surface area, would occur mainly if there were an increase in temperature. There is more than one way the material of the Earth can increase in temperature.

1. Friction between parts. Kinetic energy turning into heat.
2. Compression. The same internal energy compressed into a smaller volume.
3. Fission. The man made or natural (decay) of splitting atoms.
4. Chemical. Exothermic reactions, like the burning of gas or oil.
5. Electrical. During the flow of electrical current, heat can be produced.

These are some of the ways we know. But there may well be other unknown ways that energy can be produced and heat be the outcome. The most likely cause of temperature increase is fission. This creates or releases large quantities of energy and heat. The pressure at the centre of the Earth is estimated by scientists to be 3,600,000 times the air pressure at the Earth's surface; could this pressure create fission? Any nuclear fission at the centre would be unlikely to escape and would simply increase the pressure and temperature. Hence we can understand that there are good reasons to believe that the earth is getting hotter and is expanding all the time. This is taking place very slowly; over many millions of years. In this view the Earth began cooler; expanding as it gets hotter.

The theory that the Earth was once a red hot molten mass (and still is inside), then later was covered completely with ice, is untenable. The continuous flow of heat from a hotter zone to the outer cooler zone would not produce the conditions for an ice sheet to form and remain on the surface. Heat flow is always from hot zone to cool zone.

Other evidence that the Earth has developed a larger diameter and hence larger surface area, is shown by a different explanation for the current arrangement of the land masses (continents) on the Earth's surface; which are moving. The current scientific explanation is called "plate tectonics"; continental plates moving across the surface. This replaces Wegener's previous theory of continental drift; which described an older single continental mass that broke apart. Plate tectonics was proposed because Wegener's idea did not explain what caused the drift of the broken parts. What will the next scientific theory be? Will it be another result of HMB.

The plate tectonic idea accepts that there are long cracks in the middle areas of the large oceans; these have been observed. These are called "sea floor spreading zones"; which contain many underwater volcanoes and heat vents. Lava or magma is constantly pushing out from within the Earth into these zones; along with huge quantities of heat. It is evident that the sea floor has become wider due to these cracks pushing out magma; thus increasing the surface area of the planet, and splitting the continental land mass.

Atlantic ocean

Indian ocean

Pacific ocean

If the earth previously had one larger continental mass with sea all around it, then it could have broken apart as the diameter of the earth became larger. i.e. the stretching of the surface. This may account for the cracks in the oceans; which are filling up with magma as the ocean floor gets wider. We could combine Wegener's idea with the tectonic plate idea and show that a combination of drift of continents on the surface of the mantle magma, with the widening of the sea floor due to the Earth's expansion, is the cause of the current arrangement of the continental areas.

deep sea vents

white deep sea vents (warm)

deep sea vent diagram

dark deep sea vents (hot - 400°C)

If the increase in the Earth's temperature along with the increase in its diameter is accepted, then we have a single explanation for the current situation. (1) the Earth becoming spherical (2) the gaps between the continents (3) and the movement of the land masses across the surface. The wide range of creatures living near or within the vent areas, in total darkness, shows that the Earth has intelligence distinct from that of the sun.

Above there is ample evidence to show that the Earth is getting hotter and expanding.

ICE AGES

According to scientists the earth previously had very long ice ages. During one of the oldest, apparently 500 million years ago, the earth was completely covered with ice. This means it would be a completely white object in space. Therefore, as it is thought that previous ice ages were between 30,000 and 50,000 years in length, then it shows that the white colour was reflecting the heat or energy from the sun, so that the ice could not be melted. This is clear because the heat from the sun did not melt the ice away during all that time. Put your hand on a white surface in sunshine, then on a dark coloured one.

We cannot presume the Earth was spherical at that time. If it was spherical this would indicate that it was molten inside (surface tension), which in turn assumes there would be heat enough to melt the ice away in time; as it is known today, that heat from within the Earth is constantly passing out to the surface. It is doubtful that the Earth was spherical 500 million years ago. But we cannot know this from observation; only common sense.

If heat from the sun could not melt the ice, then it must be heat from within which eventually did this. As soon as there are large enough areas of land exposed to the sun, then this would allow heat from the sun to warm the surface (dark coloured surface). As the Earth became warmer and warmer inside and from the outside, then the ice age would recede. Eventually the heat would create a molten mass in the core and turning the shape from irregular into spherical. This heat would be coming from the life or consciousness within the Earth. Scientist would attribute this heat as coming from atomic fission etc.

However from the Yoga Vasishtha we have:-

9:14 -- The disembodied free spirit neither rises nor sets, --- It becomes the earth and supports these numerous types of beings.

13:7 -- The Consciousness that is the soul of the universe creates the earth and all other things.

9:7 -- The one Intelligence is the earth, heaven and nether world.

THE LIFE OF A PLANET

When a human egg is fertilised something happens inside the egg. A motionless egg has been invaded by a living mobile sperm. This sperm is conscious, hence the process of forming a human body begins. The egg is now infected with consciousness which is life.

If there were no consciousness within the egg cell, the foetus would not know to begin cell division. Also the presence of intelligence along with consciousness informs the various cells how to divide and form the various organs, bone frame and skin of the new body etc. Eventually this new body grows too big for the space it is contained in and seeks to escape. Then it has the ability to add and digest new material into itself (food) and to create heat so that it can survive.

The Earth also has the ability to add new material to itself; apparently about 40,000 tonnes of material from space is added to the Earth each year. Over many billions of years this would become a considerable increase in mass. Also currently over 100 large asteroids pass near the Earth each year. Over billions of years many hundreds of thousands may have landed on to Earth's surface. We cannot ignore this possibility. Look at a picture of the moon's surface with all its craters. How do you think they got there?

The consciousness within the Earth would also give it the ability to create heat; as with the new foetus before and after its birth; and as with the sun. If scientists say that it is chemical processes which create heat in the human body, this avoids talking about the thing they have little concept of - viz consciousness. Since we need consciousness to study it - making it difficult to study.

The many 1,000s year old Brihadaranyaka Upanishad states (verse 3:4:2.) :-

" --- You cannot see that which is the witness of vision; you cannot hear that which is the hearer of hearing, you cannot think that which is the thinker of thought; you cannot know that which is the knower of knowledge. ----"

This shows we cannot know consciousness easily.

We know a human body cools quickly after consciousness has left it (death). If we think that the heat is due to chemical processes, i.e. unconscious physical interactions, then why could these not carry on in a body with no conscious being within it? We have to accept that it is consciousness which is life and is that which produces heat; or maintains the chemical processes. This same consciousness produces heat in the sun and the Earth.

I have already stated that the sun is thought to be a living being; here we need to ponder the possibility that the Earth is also a living conscious being, with intelligence. As such it knows more about its life than we can ever know. And can control the climate.

To sum up the above :- Consciousness creates a planet and dwells within it. The planet has a life process and needs to develop itself, as a foetus does from an egg. During this development it gathers material for its growth and develops the ability to warm itself from within. As it warms sufficiently it sheds the ice covering, becomes molten inside then slowly becomes spherical, expands and produces seas and land surfaces. Then it activates the mystical ability to create conscious living life forms on its surface.

The above echoes partly an old familiar writing : (my comments in brackets).

2. And the earth was without form (i.e. not spherical) and void (of living creatures).

7. And God made the firmament (area of the sky) and divided the waters which were under the firmament from the waters which were above the firmament (vapour in space).

9. And God said let the waters under the heaven be gathered together unto one place (make seas), and let the dry land appear.

11. And God said let the earth bring forth grass, the herb yielding seed, and the tree yielding fruit --- etc. (The Earth can only do this if it is conscious.)
[Genesis = beginning Chpt. 1] God = consciousness.

The difficulty is, the idiotic belief in Darwinism, which has never been proved. This prevents scientists etc. from understanding how life forms appear, as described in the above ancient writings. The fact that the Earth (or Mother Nature) can spontaneously produce life forms is far from the minds of those who believe in Darwinism - see the section on Darwin's theory in HMB. Then you may understand that it is an illusion.

For hundreds of years human beings have been documenting the various animal species on the planet. Some people devote their whole life to particular species. Yet more than 15,000 new species of animals are discovered each year, in this century. These include many insects, reptiles, mammals, birds and snakes. The same happens with new plants. How do we know these new ones have not been spontaneously created?

It could be said that the above verses were an ancient attempt to describe the process of the creation of the Earth and the creatures on its surface. Yet we do not know what is lost in translation. After all, the big-bang theory is not much different. According to scientists the whole universe was supposed to have spontaneously appeared at single point in space; from there being nothing before. How is that any different from the spontaneous appearance of fully functioning planets, suns and living creatures?

Scientists view of life on earth appearing is stated as:-

“ – a few hundred million years after this process (of the earth being formed) – around 2.2 billion to 2.7 billion years ago – photosynthesizing bacteria evolved.”

Evolved from what? Do they not mean “spontaneously appeared”? The DNA of bacteria is as complex as the DNA of a human being. Why would it therefore be different to saying:- “---2.7 billion years later human beings evolved (or suddenly appeared).” ?

We do not know the capabilities of consciousness, because we cannot study it.

"For I say unto you, that God (consciousness) is able of these stones to raise up children unto Abraham. (can create human beings from stones)" Luke 3: 8. - the words of Jesus (my comments in brackets)

The above statement was by a very wise and knowledgeable person. It indicates that Mother Nature (God) has the capability of producing any creature at any place and at any time. This knowledge was not within the scope of fame seekers like Charles Darwin.

If we believe the scientist view that :- (a) The universe spontaneously appeared ; and (b) Photosynthesizing bacteria spontaneously appeared, then we would be consistent in believing that the creation itself (through consciousness) has the capacity to embody the consciousness of a divine being; such as Shri Krishna or Jesus Christ into a human form. And this for the purpose of letting us know what is going on behind the scenes of the creation process. Trust in those greater than ourselves would bear fruit in our lives.

If we have got that far in keeping our internal belief mechanism consistent, then we should not doubt the ancient statements quoted above; and accept them as valuable information in understanding how the sun and the Earth are conscious beings.

The presence of living creatures on any planet is only the middle stage of its life. When it gets hotter it will produce an environment in which organic creatures cannot survive. Then it will begin to glow with heat, in the same way Jupiter is glowing at present; and radiating energy to its moons. Having become much bigger, a planet will have collected many moons (potential planets) around it. As the sun did before it began to shine. When any planet bursts into spontaneous brightness, it will become a sun. Then its

moons become planets. As will happen to Jupiter in future. Then the sun and Jupiter will push away from each other (opposing solar winds) but stay together in space and rotate around each other; as many binary star systems do at present. There are more multiple star systems than solitary suns like ours. New stars (suns) are appearing in our galaxy all the time. All other galaxies form new stars continuously. Scientists cannot explain this phenomena; and do not understand they are witnessing this process close at hand in this solar system, with the planet Jupiter. But events that take very many human lifetimes to happen cannot really be studied, or believed, by such people as scientists.

This is the life of a planet - to eventually become a sun. But no one will wish to believe it, as it means organic life on Earth will cease; as it has already on Jupiter. But souls can travel anywhere in the galaxy faster than any spaceship; faster than light; in fact instantaneously. Now it is beginning to sound like the "Hitchhiker's Guide". Perhaps I am as crazy as Douglas Adams. We should not fear death; that which is the human being is immutable, and can be embodied any where in any creature and at any time.

And because a soul is consciousness, it can produce organic life on any suitable planet. Of which there are hundreds of millions to chose from. We know, by using our consciousness, our present life here on this planet; but we do not know from which planet we came so as to be here. This is hidden from us. When a planet provides suitable conditions then it attracts souls from all around. These subjects are beyond scientists' understanding. But not beyond the comprehension of one who can think clearly.

CLIMATE CHANGE

All theories about climate change centre around a single fact; that of an increase in the temperature of the air surrounding the earth combined with a rise in the sea temperatures. These two are part and parcel of each other. The main subject is the increase in certain gases which slow down the escape of heat from the earth's atmosphere. These are called "greenhouse gases" due to the effect they have of making the earth's atmosphere like a greenhouse, where the sun's heat is trapped. But is this the whole story?

Carbon dioxide (50%), methane (40%) and water vapour are the main greenhouse gases. They trap the heat coming from the earth's surface, preventing it from escaping into space. Without them the air temperatures would be well below freezing across the planet (about -18°C). Hence it is the intelligence of Mother Nature to produce these gases naturally, so that organic life can exist on the planets surface. Yet, due to the focus on gases, have we missed other factors which cause air temperatures to rise?

The climate change protagonists seem to have ignored the thousands of miles of cracks in the earths surface on the ocean floors, which are undersea volcanoes. Discovered only in 1977, there are many hundreds of miles of deep sea vents pouring vast quantities of heat into the oceans; 24/7 or 365 days a year. This may or may not be due to the issues I have discussed above. But the fact remains that heat from within the Earth has been pouring into the water of the oceans for an unknown number of millennia. The temperature near the vents can be as high as 400 °C. This temperature is possible due to the high pressure. It is hot enough to melt some metals. This has surely raised the temperature of the oceans. But it does not seem to have cooled the inside of the Earth; surface volcanoes are common occurrences.

The life forms which live near the super hot deep sea vents defy the scientists view that. *"Without the sun - life as we know it could not exist here on our home planet."* Genetically the life forms are as complex as *"life as we know it"*. And they exists without sunlight. This shows that consciousness exists in the Earth independent of the that in the sun.

Whatever the mean temperature of the oceans is currently, it is certain that this temperature was much lower one million years ago; evidence of ice covering large areas. The oceans are the greatest area of air temperature control on the planet earth. Hence the intelligence of the planet has the ability to control climate. Human contribution may well be small by comparison. But scientist appear not to have factored into climate change statements the effect of the heat from within the Earth affecting the climate.

We are like Arthur Dent in the HGTTG, believing we are greater than Mother Nature and panicking because we fear the destruction of life on earth. We cannot change the course of nature, we have no such power. We need not fear death. All life originated from consciousness in the beginning. Consciousness is indestructible, hence life will continue wherever it decides to carry out the plan of the universe.

CONCLUSION

We will naturally try to influence climate change with our human effort. But this should be measured against the enormous forces of Nature, which we have no power over. If readers do not wish to accept the various statements above, which include consciousness, then at least try to put together the physical and other facts, which we know to be true. And reach a non-scientific conclusion using common sense.

1. Doubts about the conclusions of scientists due to the effect of HMB.
2. Ice ages diminishing - with the cause not being fully explained by scientists.
3. The sea floor expansion zones, showing Earth's area expansion.
4. Heat from within coming to the surface of the land and heating the oceans.
5. Perhaps the planet and all life forms will adapt to higher temperatures.

If we combine these things (join up the dots), which we can verify by the use of intellect, it must become clear that there are other contributory factors, which add to human activity, to cause changes in the climate temperature across the planet.

Looking at the three diagrams below. You may not be able to see what the object is from the first picture. But if we put numbers to the dots, as in the second. Then join them up in order, as in the third. The picture becomes clearly that of a cockerel.

1. no numbers

2. with numbers

3. picture

All scientists learn how to do this as children. But when they grow up, they put away childish things. This document is nothing more than joining up a few dots, which all live in the separate boxes of various scientific minds.

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Pictures taken from www and edited / enhanced by the author.